

Findability of Cultural Heritage Datasets

Summary of research report by Kanika Makhija

In its first six months, Task Group 2.3 of the SSHOC_NL project focused on its aim “to allow researchers to find heritage and cultural data that currently are available in the dataset registry of the Network Digital Heritage (NDE), and the EHRI Portal”. To understand the challenges faced by Social Science and Humanities (SSH) researchers when searching for and accessing datasets, KB intern Kanika Makhija conducted 22 user interviews addressing the following questions:

1. What is the user experience of SSH researchers with the discovery of cultural heritage datasets?
2. How is this experience influenced by the preferences, domain knowledge and technical expertise of SSH researchers?

The participants were recruited from our network, meaning they were already familiar with cultural heritage datasets and data registries, so they are not representative of all SSH researchers. Nevertheless, the findings provide insights into specific needs and preferences of SSH researchers and suggest potential solutions to improve their user experiences.

1. User Experience

Overall, participants expressed satisfaction with their experience. However, several key challenges were identified related to

- Accessibility
- Findability
- System knowledge
- Technical barriers
- Usability

Table 6: Sentiment based of database experience

Experience	Negative	Neutral	Positive
Accessibility Experience	17	19	7
Findability experience	26	51	19
System Knowledge	5	14	5
Technical barrier	14	16	1
Usability Experience	21	18	15

Accessibility: Participants frequently mentioned challenges related to the complexity of accessing data, with copyright restrictions being the most significant drawback. Platforms that require expensive contracts for limited data were also criticized. Additionally, participants noted difficulties when requests for access to repositories went unanswered. When specific project requirements necessitated building a custom dataset, the process became cumbersome, often leading to arbitrary decisions. Re-using research datasets was also challenging due to the lack of standardized formats.

Participants who understood these limitations had neutral experiences, accepted them as part of the project, and found workarounds. Positive feedback was limited, typically focuses on platforms and institutions that provides structured datasets or a secure environment for interacting with and analyzing protected data, even if it these platforms were challenging to learn. Restricted access to datasets was accepted when it provided clear data management rules.

Findability: Most participants expressed neutral sentiments, noting that after considerable effort, they were able to navigate the system and locate the required datasets. A steep learning curve was evident, with some participants resorting to web crawlers and internet scraping tools to acquire data. Negative experiences arose from inconsistent dataset descriptions leading to friction or outright failure in locating specific datasets, and outdated or unchecked interlinked datasets.

System knowledge: Users who understood how database repository are organized found it easier to obtain accurate results. Many reported having to invest extra effort, such as learning the language of librarians and archivists, identifying reliable sources, or adjusting search across collections. Establishing contact with database administrators for specific metadata requests led to more successful outcomes, but only after initial frustration.

Technical barriers: Technical issues were a common frustration, including redundancy (the same object or data item appearing in multiple repositories), incomplete details and outdated and unavailable registries. The limited availability of reusable research datasets also contributed to neutral or negative feedback.

Usability: Negative feedback was primarily related to missing or malfunctioning features, such as inadequate documentation, incorrect dataset titles, and display or interface issues. In contrast, platforms with simple features, clean interfaces, and easy access to collections received positive feedback.

2. Technical expertise and educational background

Users with higher technical proficiency were generally better equipped to navigate the platforms but were also more critical of the features and services.

Participants learned about databases through projects, universities, colleagues, literature searches, search engines, and forums. Academic institutions played a crucial role in providing access to databases, while professional networks helped guide researchers to relevant databases through shared experiences and recommendations. This applied to participants across different technical skill levels, from Master's students to PhD holders.

3. User preferences and needs

The interviews revealed several areas for improvement to enhance the utility and accessibility of datasets. Key needs include:

- Richer metadata and more flexible, customizable options for specific research projects
- Collaborative tools for working on research projects
- Better communication on platforms
- Improved resource allocation and metadata management
- Secure environments for data sharing
- Clear and consistent dataset referencing
- Quick-start guides for new users
- Better integration and centralization of data across platforms

Most participants had adopted a pragmatic approach, accepting the limitations of existing tools and datasets as part of the process.

The full report can be viewed [here](#).

https://hbo-kennisbank.nl/details/sharekit_ahk:
oai:surfsharekit.nl:f7744f63-bf9c-4d35-8edd-af95821f95b0

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